

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF COST, RETURNS, PROFITABILITY AND MARKETING CHANNELS, PRICE SPREAD OF PEARL MILLET PRODUCTION IN BEED DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA STATE

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Abstract

The investigation was carried out during the year 2020-21 on economics of production and marketing of pearl millet in Beed district of Maharashtra State. The multistage sampling method adopted in selection of district, tehsils, villages and selection of pearl millet growers. The 60 pearl millet producers were chosen for the research. The data was analysed using techniques such as mean percentage, ratio and cost concept of cost-A, cost-B, and cost-C. The per hectare cost of cultivation was i.e cost C was ₹ 39439.9 in which cost-A was ₹ 27073.26 and cost-B was ₹ 38176.48. The output-input ratio was 1.25. The net profit was 10192.09 and per quintal cost of production was ₹ 2321.70. The Ambajogai and Dharur markets were selected for marketing of pearl millet. The marketing channel-I having producer- consumer, in which the marketing cost of producer was ₹ 36.41 and price spread was ₹ 36.41. The channel-II was producer- village retailer -consumer. In which the marketing cost was ₹87.66 and price spread was ₹ 289.66. The channel-III that is producer-wholesaler-retailer-consumer. In which marketing cost was ₹ 232.65 and price spread was ₹ 504.33.

Key words : Cost of cultivation, Marketing channel, Net profit, Gross returns, Marketing cost

Introduction

Pennisetum glaucum is the botanical name for pearl millet. It belongs to the Graminae family. Bajra is the popular name for it. Bajra is thought to have originated in tropical Africa. Following then, cultivation extended to East and Southern Africa, as well as Southern Asia. It is the most widely cultivated millet type within the millet group. Pearl millet offers a lot of benefits that have made it popular. In hot semiarid climates, it is the traditional staple grain crop for subsistence or low-resource agriculture. Drought, low soil fertility, and high temperatures characterise this production system. It works well in soils with high salinity or low pH. It is also known as pearl millet or cattail. In English, millet is known as spiked millet. In Tamilnadu, it is known as 'Kampu'. In Arabic, dukheri and in Africa, mahangu. Bajra is the world's sixth most significant cereal crop after wheat, rice, maize, barley, and sorghum. Pearl millet has many benefits including being high in magnesium which helps to keep the heart healthy. Insoluble fibre is abundant in bajra. It is suitable for diabetics. In India, the production value of pearl millet was 10.49 million metric tons in the financial year 2020-2021. There was an increase in production as compared to previous financial year 2018-2019 in which the production value was 8.66 million metric tons. (Source- statista.com). India is the world's leading producer of pearl millet. In India pearl millet crop covers area 7.65 million ha of land, with total production of 10.86 million tons and productivity of 1420 (kg/ha) in the year 2020-2021.(Source- indiastatagri.com). In Maharashtra during the year 2020-21 the area, production and productivity of pearl millet was 6.87 lakh ha, 6.56 lakh tonnes and 955.00 kg/ha, respectively.

(Source- indiastatagri.com)**Objectives**

1. To estimate per hectare cost, returns and profitability of pearl millet crop.
2. To study the marketing channel and price spread in pearl millet marketing.

Materials and Methods

The district, tehsils, villages, and pearl millet growers were chosen using a multistage sample design. To collect data on production, cost, returns, marketing channel, marketing cost, and other factors, 60 pearl millet growers were chosen. The information was gathered for the fiscal year 2020-21. Beed district was chosen for the study in the

Table 1: Per hectare physical input and output of pearl millet farm (Unit/ha)

Sr.No.	Particulars	Unit	Quantity
INPUT			
1.	Hired human labour	man days	
	Male		7.36
	Female		18.87
2.	Family human labour	man days	

first round because it ranked top in terms of area and production in Marathwada region of Maharashtra state. In the second step, two tehsils from Beed district, Ambajogai and Dharur, were chosen for the collecting year 2021 on the basis of increased area under pearl millet production and researcher convenience.

In the third stage, three villages viz., Dongar pimpla, Rajewadi and Umrai from Ambajogai tehsil and Aasardoh, Anjandhav and Pimparwada from Dharur tehsil randomly were selected. All six villages were taken into account. As a result, six villages from two tahsils were chosen for the current study. In the fourth stage 10 pearl millet growers were randomly selected from each selected villages. Thus from 6 villages, 60 pearl millet growers were selected. To ensure cooperation, the sample farmers were personally interviewed and the study's aims were outlined. The data was gathered by a survey method using a properly planned and pre-tested schedule. The time table detailing the socioeconomic features of pearl millet growers, cropping pattern, physical input, cost of various expenditures, and so on. For the 2020-21 crop year, the return was received. In addition, data was examined using in relation to the study's goal. The second objective i.e. marketing channels and price spread of pearl millet marketing was achieved by tabular analysis technique. The Ambajogai and Dharur market selected for marketing of pearl millet.

Results and Discussion

The findings are achieved from the current study are presented below:

Physical inputs and outputs

The per hectare physical inputs and outputs of pearl millet production were calculated and presented in table 1. It was observed that, the use of hired human labour in which male labour was 7.36 man days and female labour was 18.87 man days. The family male labour was 5.50 man days and family female labour was 1.74 man days used. The use of bullock labour was 2.16 pair days in pearl millet farm. On the contrary, use of machine labour was 7.93 hours/ha. The use of seed was 3.90 kg/ha in pearl millet farm. In regard to manure, the quantity of 2.57 quintals/ha was used in pearl millet farm. Use of urea was 46.63 kg/ha, DAP was 52.63 kg/ha, SSP was 88.80 kg/ha used in pearl millet farm. The fertilizers that is 10:26:26 was 34.14 kg/ha and fertilizer 18:18:10 was 38.57 kg/ha used in pearl millet farm. It was also observed from the Table 1. The main produce of pearl millet was 16.37 quintals/ha and by produce was 2.03 quintals/ha.

	Male		5.50
	Female		1.74
3.	Bullock labour	pair days	2.16
4.	Machine labour	hours	7.93
5.	Seed	kg	3.90
6.	Manures	qt.	2.57
7.	Fertilizers		
	Urea	kg	46.63
	DAP	kg	52.63
	SSP	kg	88.80
	10:26:26	kg	34.14
	18:18:10	kg	38.57
8.	OUTPUT		
	Main produce	qt.	16.37
	By produce	qt.	2.03

Cost of cultivation of pearl millet growers

Per hectare cost of cultivation of pearl millet were calculated and presented in table 2. The result revealed that, the per hectare cost of cultivation was ₹ 39439.97 in which Cost-A was ₹27073.26 (68.64 per cent), Cost-B was ₹ 38176.48 (96.79 per cent) and Cost-C was ₹ 39439.97 (100 per cent). The amount spent on machine labour was ₹ 5555.55 i.e.14.08 per cent. The next expenditure is rental value of land which amount to ₹ 8234.01 (20.87 per cent), hired human labour accounted for at ₹ 5459.52 (13.84 per cent), expenditure on seed was

₹ 240.74 (0.61 per cent), family labour which is accounted at ₹ 1263.49(3.20 per cent), interesting on working capital was ₹ 1312.77(3.32 per cent), expenditure on urea ₹ 279.80 (0.70 per cent), DAP ₹ 1422.33 (3.60 per cent), SSP ₹ 355.23(0.90 per cent), manure costing ₹ 4520.63 (11.46 per cent), bullock labour costing was ₹ 2007.93 (5.09 per cent), interest on fixed capital costing ₹ 2869.21(7.27 per cent),depreciation on capital assets costing was ₹ 3842.91 (9.74 per cent), land revenue was ₹ 38.00(0.09 per cent) and incidental charges were ₹ 220.00(0.55 per cent).

Table 2: Per hectare cost of cultivation of pearl millet crop (₹/ha)

Sr.No.	Particular	Amount (₹)	Per cent
1.	Hired human labour	5459.52	13.84
2.	Machine labour	5555.55	14.08
3.	Bullock labour	2007.93	5.09
4.	Seed	240.74	0.61
5.	Manure	4520.63	11.46
6.	Fertilizers		
	Urea	279.80	0.70
	DAP	1422.33	3.60
	SSP	355.23	0.90
	10:26:26	853.57	2.16
	18:18:10	964.28	2.44
7.	Land revenue	38.00	0.09
8.	Incidental charges	220.00	0.55
9.	Interest on working capital @ 6 %	1312.77	3.32
10.	Depreciation on capital assets @10%	3842.91	9.74
11.	Cost-A (Σ 1 to 10)	27073.26	68.64
12.	Rental value of land	8234.01	20.87
13.	Interest on fixed capital @10%	2869.21	7.27
14.	Cost-B (Σ 11 to 13)	38176.48	96.79
15.	Family human labour	1263.49	3.20
16.	Cost -C (Σ 14 to 15)	39439.97	100

Profitability of pearl millet

Per hectare profitability in pearl millet production was calculated and presented in table 3. The results shows that, per hectare gross return

was found to be ₹ 49632.06 in pearl millet farm. It was shows that, farm business income was ₹ 22558.80 , family labour income was ₹ 11455.58 and net profit/ha was ₹ 10192.09. It was clear that, benefit-

cost ratio was 1.25. Pearl millet crop was profitable enterprise. The per quintal cost of production of pearl millet was ₹ 2321.70 (Table 3).

Table 3 : Per hectare profitability in pearl millet production (₹/ha)

Sr.No.	Particulars	Physical unit	Physical quantity	Amount (Rs)
1.	Return from a main produce	qt	16.37	48198.33
2.	Return from by produce	qt	2.03	1433.73
3.	Gross returns	qt	18.4	49632.06
4.	Cost-A	-	-	27073.26
5.	Cost-B	-	-	38176.48
6.	Cost-C	-	-	39439.97
7.	Farm business income (Gross returns minus Cost-A)	-	-	22558.80
8.	Family labour income (Gross returns minus Cost-B)	-	-	11455.58
9.	Net Profit (Gross return minus Cost-C)	-	-	10192.09
10.	Benefit-Cost ratio (Gross return divided by Cost-C)	-	-	1.25
11.	Per quintal cost of production (Cost-C minus by produce value divided by main produce quantity)	-	-	2321.70

Fig.1: Per hectare cost of cultivation of pearl millet crop

Production, retention and marketed surplus of pearl millet

Per farm production, retention, marketed surplus and marketing of pearl millet through different marketing channels were calculated and showed in table 4. The result revealed that, the average pearl millet farm was 1.00 hectares. The pearl millet production on farm was 16.37 quintals. It was also observed that, the quantity of pearl millet retained for family consumption was 0.74 quintals and retained for

seed purpose was 0.02 quintals. The quantity of pearl millet sold in per farm through channels-I was 2.00 quintals i.e.12.22 per cent, Channel-II was 3.74 quintals i.e.22.85 per cent and channel-III was 8.59 quintals i.e.52.47 per cent. The total marketed surplus from three channels was 14.33 quintals i.e.87.54 per cent. It was observed that the highest quantities of pearl millet were marketed through channel-III i.e.8.59 quintals.

Table 4: Production, retention and marketed surplus of pearl millet through different Channels

Sr.No.	Particulars	Standards	Percentage
1.	Farm size (ha)	1.00	-
2.	Production (qt)	16.37	100
3.	Retention for family consumption	0.74	4.52

4.	Retension for seed	0.02	0.12
5.	Damage	1.28	7.82
6.	Marketed surplus in channel-I(Producer-consumer)	2.00	12.22
7.	Marketed surplus in Channel-II (Producer-village retailer-consumer)	3.74	22.85
8.	Marketed surplus in Channel -III(Producer-wholesaler-retailer-consumer)	8.59	52.47
	Total Marketed surplus	14.33	87.54

Marketing cost incurred by producer

The per quintal marketing cost of pearl millet was determined and shown in table 5. According to the results, the marketing cost incurred by producer was greater in channel III at ₹116.58, marketing cost incurred by producer was ₹ 47.71 in channel II and marketing cost incurred by producer was ₹ 36.41 in channel I. The expenditure in channel I was for transportation cost was ₹ 8.89 (24.41 per cent), followed by unloading cost was ₹ 8.15 (22.39 per cent), loading cost was ₹ 8.00 (21.97 per cent), packaging cost was ₹ 6.37 (17.50 per cent) and weighing cost was ₹ 5.00 (13.73 per cent). The expenditure in channel II was on transportation cost was the highest at ₹ 13.72

(28.75 per cent) followed by unloading cost was ₹ 10.00 (20.96 per cent), packing cost was ₹ 10.00 (20.95 per cent), loading cost was ₹ 9.00 (18.86 per cent) and charges for weighing ₹ 5.00 (10.48 per cent). Similar to this, in channel III, cost incurred by producer on commission fees was ₹ 36.57 (31.37 per cent) followed by transportation fees was ₹ 33.18 (28.46 per cent), loading fees was ₹ 11.31 (9.70 per cent), packing fees was ₹ 10.00 (8.58 per cent), unloading fees was ₹ 8.96 (7.69 per cent), deduction cost was ₹ 8.42 (7.22 per cent), weighing fees was ₹ 5.47 (4.69 per cent) and market fee was ₹ 2.67 (2.29 per cent).

Table 5: Marketing cost of pearl millet incurred by producer (₹/q)

Sr.No.	Particulars	Channel-I	Channel-II	Channel-III
1.	Loading charges	8.00 (21.97)	9.00 (18.86)	11.31 (9.70)
2.	Transport charges	8.89 (24.41)	13.72 (28.75)	33.18 (28.46)
3.	Unloading charges	8.15 (22.39)	10.00 (20.96)	8.96 (7.69)
4.	Weighing charges	5.00 (13.73)	5.00 (10.48)	5.47 (4.69)
5.	Packing charges	6.37 (17.50)	10.00 (20.95)	10.00 (8.58)
6.	Commission charges	-	-	36.57 (31.37)
7.	Market fee	-	-	2.67 (2.29)
8.	Deduction	-	-	8.42 (7.22)
	Total cost incurred by producer	36.41 (100)	47.71 (100)	116.58 (100)

Marketing cost incurred by village retailer (₹/q)

The per quintal marketing costs of pearl millet incurred by village retailer were computed and shown in table 6. The total marketing cost incurred by village retailer in channel II was ₹ 39.95 per quintal. The labour charges having biggest amount in channel II i.e. ₹ 12.91

(32.32 per cent), followed by transportation charges was ₹ 12.00 (30.04 per cent), packaging fees was ₹ 6.02 (15.07 per cent), weighing fees was ₹ 5.02 (12.56 per cent) and storage fees was ₹4.00 (10.01 per cent). In this channel the highest charges on transportation and lowest charges on storage.

Table 6: Marketing cost incurred by village retailer (₹/q)

Sr.No.	Particulars	Channel-I	Channel-II	Channel-III
1.	Labour charges	-	12.91 (32.32)	-
2.	Transportation charges	-	12.00 (30.04)	-
3.	Weighing charges	-	5.02 (12.56)	-
4.	Storage charges	-	4.00 (10.01)	-
5.	Packing charges	-	6.02 (15.07)	-
	Total cost incurred by village retailer	-	39.95 (100)	-

Marketing cost incurred by wholesaler (₹/q)

The per quintal marketing cost of pearl millet incurred by the wholesaler with respect of various particulars in channel III was computed and shown in table 7. The total marketing cost incurred by the wholesaler in channel III was ₹ 60.77 per quintal. In channel III, the cost of transportation was the highest at ₹15.00 (24.68 per cent)

followed by the cost of labour was ₹ 12.07(19.86 per cent), cost of losses was ₹ 12.07 (19.86 per cent), cost of stall rental was ₹ 6.00 (9.87 per cent), cost of storage was ₹ 5.00 (8.23 per cent), cost of electricity was ₹ 4.43 (7.29 per cent), cost of market fees was ₹ 3.00 (4.94 per cent), cost of licencing was ₹ 2.90 (4.77 per cent) and cost of communication was ₹ 0.30 (0.49 per cent) in channel III.

Table 7: Marketing cost incurred by wholesaler (₹/q)

Sr.No.	Particulars	Channel-I	Channel-II	Channel-III
1.	Stall rent	-	-	6.00 (9.87)
2.	License charges	-	-	2.90 (4.77)
3.	Labour charges	-	-	12.07 (19.86)
4.	Electric charges	-	-	4.43 (7.29)
5.	Transportation charges	-	-	15.00 (24.68)
6.	Market fee	-	-	3.00 (4.94)
7.	Communication charges	-	-	0.30 (0.49)
8.	Losses	-	-	12.07 (19.86)
9.	Storage charges	-	-	5.00 (8.23)
	Total cost incurred by wholesaler	-	-	60.77 (100)

Marketing cost incurred by retailer

The per quintal marketing cost of pearl millet incurred by the retailer was calculated and showed in table 8. The cost incurred by the retailer in channel-III was higher at ₹ 55.30 with the highest proportional expenditure on transportation cost was ₹ 13.82 (24.99 per cent) followed by packing and storage cost was ₹ 11.92 (21.55 per cent), labour cost was ₹ 13.05 (23.60 per cent), shop tax was ₹ 8.00 (14.46 per cent), electronic cost was ₹ 4.02 (7.27 per cent) and licence cost was ₹ 4.50 (8.13 per cent).

Table 8: Marketing cost incurred by retailer (₹/q)

Sr.No.	Particulars	Channel-I	Channel-II	Channel-III
1.	Shop tax	-	-	8.00 (14.46)
2.	License charges	-	-	4.50 (8.13)
3.	Labour charges	-	-	13.05 (23.60)
4.	Electronic charges	-	-	4.02 (7.27)
5.	Transportation charges	-	-	13.82 (24.99)
6.	Packing with storage	-	-	11.92 (21.55)
	Total cost incurred by retailer	-	-	55.30 (100)

Price spread in pearl millet marketing

Per quintal marketing costs, marketing margins, and price spreads in the marketing of pearl millet through various channels were calculated and presented in table 9. The result revealed that the total marketing cost in channel I was ₹ 36.41. The expenses incurred by the producer was ₹ 36.41. Net price received by the producer was ₹ 2998.59 (98.80 per cent) and the price paid by the consumer was ₹ 3035.00. The price spread in this channel was ₹ 36.41 i.e.1.19 per cent.

In channel II, the total marketing cost was ₹ 87.66 it consist of marketing cost incurred by the producer and village retailer. The margin of village retailer was ₹ 202.00. The price received by the producer from village retailer was ₹ 2798.05 while the producer cost was ₹ 47.71. The cost and margin incurred by village retailer were ₹ 39.95 and ₹ 202.00 respectively. The price paid by the consumer was

₹ 3040.00. Therefore, a price spread was ₹ 289.66. The producer share in consumer rupee in channel II was ₹ 90.47 per cent. The total marketing margin in channel II were ₹ 202.00 and the price spread in this channel was ₹ 289.66 i.e.9.52 per cent.

In channel-III, that the price paid by consumer in this channel was ₹ 3075.00. It was clear that, the price received by the producer from wholesaler was ₹ 2687.25 while cost incurred by producer was ₹ 116.58. In next order, cost incurred by the wholesaler was ₹ 60.77 while marketing margin of wholesaler was ₹ 95.83. The wholesaler had sold the produce to retailer at ₹ 2843.89. Next order, cost incurred by retailer was ₹ 55.30 while marketing margin was ₹ 175.85 and thus it inferred that, in this channel the total marketing cost was ₹ 232.65 while total marketing margin was ₹ 271.68 and the price spread was found to be ₹ 504.33. It inferred that, price spread was found higher in channel-III as compared to channel-I and channel-II.(Table 9).

Table 9: Per quintal Marketing cost, Market margin and price spread of pearl millet (₹/q)

Sr.No.	Particulars	Channel-I	Channel-II	Channel-III
1.	Net price received by producer (producer share in consumer rupee)	2998.59 (98.80)	2750.34 (90.47)	2570.67 (83.59)
2.	Expenses incurred by producer	36.41 (1.19)	47.71 (1.56)	116.58 (3.79)
3.	Price paid by village retailer	-	2798.05 (92.04)	-
4.	Expenses incurred by village retailer	-	39.95 (1.31)	-
5.	Margin of village retailer	-	202.00 (6.64)	-
6.	Price paid by wholesaler	-	-	2687.25 (87.39)
7.	Expenses incurred by wholesaler	-	-	60.77 (1.97)
8.	Margin of wholesaler	-	-	95.83 (3.11)
9.	Price paid by retailer	-	-	2843.89 (92.48)
10.	Expenses incurred by retailer	-	-	55.30 (1.79)
11.	Margin of retailer	-	-	175.85 (5.71)
12.	Price paid by consumer	3035.00 (100)	3040.00 (100)	3075.00 (100)
13.	Marketing cost	36.41 (1.19)	87.66 (2.88)	232.65 (7.56)
14.	Marketing margin	-	202.00 (6.64)	271.68 (8.83)
15.	Price spread	36.41 (1.19)	289.66 (9.52)	504.33 (16.40)

Conclusion

The per hectare use of hired female labour was 18.87 man days and SSP that is 88.80 kg. The per hectare cost of cultivation of pearl millet crop was ₹ 39439.97 and net profit in pearl millet cultivation was ₹ 10192.09. The benefit- cost ratio of pearl millet crop was 1.25. The farm business income was ₹ 22558.80, family labour income was ₹ 11455.58. The per quintal cost of production was ₹ 2321.70.

In channel-I, the price paid by consumer was ₹ 3035.00 and producer share in consumer rupee was 98.80 per cent. In channel-II, the price paid by consumer was ₹ 3040.00 and producer share in consumer rupee was 90.47 per cent. In channel-III, price paid by consumer was ₹ 3075.00 and producer share in consumer rupee was 83.59 per cent. The marketing cost incurred by the producer in channel-I was ₹ 36.41 per quintal, channel-II was ₹ 47.71 per quintal and in channel-III was ₹ 116.58 per quintal. The marketing cost incurred by the retailer in channel-II and channel-III were ₹ 39.95 and ₹ 55.30 per quintal respectively. The price spread in channel-I was ₹ 36.41 per quintal, in channel-II was ₹ 289.66 per quintal and in channel-III was ₹ 504.33 per quintal.

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